

evolve, educational systems must embrace these innovative tools to enhance learning experiences.

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TEACHING LISTENING IN THE 21ST CENTURY: INNOVATIONS AND BEST PRACTICES

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***Abstract.** Teaching listening is the most important part of the learning journey. In the past, both students and teachers suffer from problems while*

listening classes. The first reason for this shortcoming was the lack of technology and ineffective methods. However, today this tendency has changed a lot with the introduction of new devices and modern methods. Integrating digital tools, interactive platforms, and authentic audio resources helps teachers to enhance student's engagement and comprehension. Not only technologies can be considered useful during classes but also modern pedagogical strategies like flipped classroom, gamification, and personalized approaches can be critical during listening lessons. Although there are enough researches have been done on this topic, I have asked some teachers about the challenges they face and which techniques and devices help them during difficulties.

Keywords. *Digital tools, flipped classroom, gamification, communication, personalized teaching, proficiency level, interactive, podcasts, listening comprehension.*

Introduction. Listening is a foundational skill in language learning and communication. In the 21st century, rapid development of technologies and globalization has considerably altered the way listening is taught and learned. Some traditional methods usually fail to solve the problems of today's learners, who require more engaging and interactive lessons. Listening is the most important and the most challenging skill to teach at the same time. Using podcasts and speech recognition software helps to overcome these problems above. This article aims to explore the impact and differences of these technologies and techniques, during listening classes. By reading this article, both teachers and students find some effective methods and useful devices to use during listening lessons.

Some scientists made research on different methods of teaching listening. For example, personalized teaching. It is the best way of teaching these days as it makes the process easy and offers chance to teachers to highlight the weaknesses of learner along with their strength. Given as an example, Shute and Zapata-Rivera suggested one of their works that "For example, adaptive learning platforms analyze students' progress and provide customized listening materials that align with their proficiency level (Shute & Zapata-Rivera, 2010). This approach ensures that students receive targeted practice, which boosts confidence and improves

outcomes." They also added that "Personalized learning not only accommodates diverse learner needs but also fosters independent and effective listening skill development." In my survey, 60% of teachers suggested to use personalized learning, in fact it has significant effect on student's progress. Moreover, gamification techniques also help to motivate students as McGonigal said in one book "Gamification techniques such as points, leaderboards, and challenges have been shown to increase intrinsic motivation, making listening exercises more enjoyable and impactful. Research highlights that gamified tasks encourage active participation, which is crucial for mastering listening comprehension (McGonigal, 2011). " This person also concluded, saying gamifying listening activities can transform a traditionally passive skill into an interactive and rewarding experience. In addition, flipped classroom can be practical which is usually conducted by showing videos and podcasts before the class begins instead of giving homework after the lecture or practical lessons. Meanwhile, podcasts are also valuable tool in enhancing engagement, listening skills and education. 'Podcasts help students focus on auditory content, improving their ability to comprehend and retain information. This skill is essential for academic success and future careers, where listening and communication are critical'. These sentences are from an article called '6 benefits of listening to podcasts for students'. Additionally, podcasts offer flexible learning and availability. 'One of the greatest advantages of education podcasts is their portability and convenience. Podcasts can be downloaded to a mobile device, allowing the student to access the learning resources anytime, anywhere, with very little effort'. By using podcasts during lessons, educators can make listening more flexible, engaging and effective. It also helps learners to build confidence in communication.

In conclusion, the integration of modern approaches such as gamification, personalized learning, flipped classrooms, and digital tools like podcasts significantly enhances the teaching of listening skills in the 21st century. These

innovations not only include diverse learning styles but also make lessons more engaging. Gamification motivates students with interactive activities, while personalized approaches create the learning experience to individual needs. Flipped classrooms maximize in-class interactions, encouraging active learning and collaboration. Podcasts especially offer authentic, accessible, and convenient resources that help students develop critical listening and comprehension skills at their own pace. With the help of these best practices, educators can create dynamic and inclusive environments that prepare learners for real-world communication challenges.

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ADDRESSING THE NEEDS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS WITH LIMITED PRIOR KNOWLEDGE

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***Abstract.** This paper examines the unique challenges faced by primary school students who are beginning their journey in foreign language learning with limited*